

DETERMINATION OF THERMOSTABILITY OF SORBENT CONTAINING OXYGEN AND SULFUR BASED ON SILICA GEL BY THE THERMOGRAVIMETRIC METHOD

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Diphenylthiocarbazone was used as a nitrogen- and sulfur-containing ligand in this research work. The thermal stability of the resulting sorbents and their complex compounds with metals was determined by differential thermal and thermogravimetric methods on a derivatograph of the Paulik-Paulik-Erdey system at a speed of 10 deg/min, T-900, TG-200, DTA-1/10, DTG - 1/ 10 sensitivity of the galvanometer, the results of thermal stability were presented by the method of automatically recording a derivatogram on photographic paper.

Key words: DTG-1/10, TG-200, diphenylthiocarbazone, silica gel, SG-DT sorbent, Cu and Co ion.

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ТЕРМОСТАБИЛЬНОСТИ СОРБЕНТА, СОДЕРЖАЩЕГО КИСЛОРОД И СЕРУ НА ОСНОВЕ КРЕМНЕГЕЛЯ ТЕРМОГРАВИМЕТРИЧЕСКИМ МЕТОДОМ

В качестве азот- и серосодержащего лиганда в данной исследовательской работе использовался дифенилтиокарбазон. Термическую стабильность полученных сорбентов и их комплексных соединений с металлами определяли дифференциально-термическим и термогравиметрическим методами на дериватографе системы Паулика-Паулика-Эрдея со скоростью 10 град/мин, Т-900, ТГ-200, ДТА- 1/10, ДТГ - 1/10 чувствительность гальванометра, результаты термостабильности представляли методом автоматической записи дериватограммы на фотобумаге.

Ключевые слова: ДТГ-1/10, ТГ-200, дифенилтиокарбазон, силикагель, сорбент марки СГ-ДТ, ион Cu и Co.

INTRODUCTION

The object of our research is silica gel with sorption properties and N and S sorbent, synthesized with the participation of diphenylthiocarbazone (DT). During our research, the SG-DT sorbent synthesized during our research was analyzed using a LABSYS EVO STA thermogravimetric analyzer. Accordingly, 7 mg of a sample of the sorbent was taken in the form of a powder and placed in a heat-resistant crucible

made of a mixture of aluminum and platinum oxides, heated to a temperature of 20-600 °C, and its thermal stability was analyzed.

LITERARY ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Research work is being carried out worldwide aimed at immobilizing ligands containing nitrogen, phosphorus and sulfur into organic polymer and mineral matrices in order to obtain selective effective complexing sorbents [1]. Currently, many scientific studies attach great importance to the production of selective sorbents by chemical modification of silica gel [2]. Currently, global production of synthetic sorbents has doubled compared to the previous decade [3].

Ligands immobilized in a polymer matrix are widely used as sorbents in hydrometallurgy to concentrate various metal ions and neutralize waste solutions containing heavy metal ions. Currently, a large range of ionizable, complexing polymers and polymer matrices has been developed. It is known that industrial methods for producing such polymer ligands are polycondensation, polymerization and copolymerization of monomers with various functional groups.

It is reported that the chelate sorbent N-(2-carboxyethyl)aminomethylpolystyrene can be used for the selective extraction of Cu^{2+} ions from multicomponent solutions containing Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions [4]. An anion exchanger based on allyl bromide, epichlorohydrin and polyethylenimine has selectivity in the sorption of Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} ions from sulfate solutions [5]. An anion resin based on aniline, epichlorohydrin and polyethylene polyamine was used for the selective separation of Cu^{2+} ions in the presence of Co^{2+} ions [6].

Immobilization of various organic ligands on various sorbents is widely used in industrial production and analytical chemistry; however, it has limitations related to contamination and safety [7]. Sorbents with immobilized ligands, such as solid-phase extractants, are environmentally and economically beneficial [8].

EXPERIMENTAL PART

The synthesized SG-DT sorbent was analyzed on a LABSYS EVO STA thermogravimetric analyzer. Accordingly, 7 mg of powder was taken from a sample of the sorbent and placed in a heat-resistant crucible made of a mixture of aluminum and platinum oxides. Thermal analysis was conducted at 600°C for 1 hour and the following results were obtained (Figure 1).

According to the analysis results, from the 3.46th minute of the process, when the temperature reached 62.99 °C, the substance began to lose mass. When the temperature increased to 200 °C in 17.35 minutes, the sorbent lost 6.146% of its mass, i.e. decreased to 0.426 mg.

Figure 1. Differential thermal analysis of SG-DT brand sorbent

After this, heating continued. At 37.65 minutes into the thermal analysis process, the heating was increased to 400°C. When the temperature reached 400 °C, the substance lost another 3.766% of its mass, ie 0.261 mg. From the 37.65th to the 60th minute of the thermal analysis process, the temperature was increased to 600 °C. When the temperature reached 600 °C, the substance lost another 2.741%, i.e. 0.190 mg mass.

It can be seen that the SG-DT sorbent lost a total of 12.653% - 0.877 mg of mass when the temperature increased from 20 °C to 600 °C for 1 hour. It can be concluded that the synthesized sorbent is heat-resistant and has high resistance to thermal effects, which is explained by the fact that it is a silica gel-based sorbent. Silica gel is a heat-resistant, stable substance that is resistant to high temperatures.

The complex compound formed by the SG-DT sorbent with metallic copper was also thermally analyzed (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Differential thermal analysis of Cu-SG-DT complex

A sample of 7.4 mg of the existing complex was taken for analysis and heated to a temperature of 20-600°C for 1 hour. As a result of differential thermal analysis, the following results were obtained:

Table 1

Thermogravimetric analysis results of Cu-SG-DT

Time (minutes)	Temperature (°C)	Decreased		Mass of residual substance (mg)
		% at the expense of	mg amount	
3,16	48,73	0	0	7,4
18,52	200,74	5,048	0,375	7,025
19,51	210,6	1,898	0.141	6,884
59,25	601,86	1,844	0,137	6,747
59,25	601,86	8,79	0,653	6,747

Based on the results of the study of this complex compound, it can be concluded that the synthesized sorbent is very resistant to thermal effects, and the Cu complex compound obtained on its basis lost less weight during thermal analysis than the corresponding sorbent. A sorbent based on silica gel has a special effect on the thermal stability of metal complexes.

Thermogravimetric analysis was also carried out on a complex combination of SG-DT sorbent with Co. Thermogravimetric analysis of the complex compound obtained from Co resulted in the following diagram:

Figure 3. Derivatogram of the results of differential thermal analysis of Co-SG-DT

A sample weighing 4.7 mg was taken for analysis. Thermal analysis was carried out by heating to 20-600°C for 1 hour. According to the results of thermal analysis, the mass of the sample decreased by 3.512% or 0.165 mg when heated to 200 °C for 17.76 minutes. It was observed that the mass began to decrease when the temperature reached 45.59 °C. By 37.86 minutes of analysis, the temperature had risen to 400°C. During

this time, 1.66% - 0.078 mg of mass was lost. The process lasted 58.33 minutes, during which time the temperature was increased to 600°C. In the temperature range 400-600 °C, the mass again decreased by 0.071 mg. It has been confirmed that the thermal stability of the complex compound containing Co is extremely high.

The results of differential thermal analysis show that the thermal stability of sorbents based on silica gel and coordination compounds based on it is extremely high, and they are not destroyed even when exposed to high temperatures. The main reason for this is due to the physical properties of silica gel.

In addition, using X-ray fluorescence spectral analysis EDX-8100 and UV spectrophotometer EMC-30PC, it is possible to determine the amount of absorbed Cu ions in a copper(II) sulfate solution of our sorbent [9].

CONCLUSION

Differential thermal analysis of the obtained sorbent and compounds formed by Cu and Co metals based on it was carried out and their thermal stability was determined.

Since silica gel is extremely resistant to thermal effects, it was made sure that the sorbents and metal complexes synthesized on its basis have a very high thermal stability.

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